

Between Moral Authority and Politics

The Confederation of Political Prisoners after the Fall of Communism in Czechoslovakia (1989–1994)

Klára Pinerová

TUD Dresden University of Technology

Hannah Arendt Institute for Totalitarianism Studies e. V. at the TU Dresden

Institute of Contemporary History, Czech Academy of Sciences

In the turbulent days of November 1989 in Czechoslovakia, former political prisoners revived the idea of establishing a new organization to advocate for their interests, drawing on the legacy of the Association of Former Political Prisoners – Club 231 (*Sdružení bývalých politických vězňů – Klub 231*, commonly referred to as K 231),¹ which they had founded during the Prague Spring of 1968. During the political upheaval of 1968, political prisoners were able to talk about their experiences of interrogation and imprisonment. In addition, the Czechoslovak communist leaders initiated discussions on the passage of a law on rehabilitation, which would have given individuals wrongly convicted of political crimes the opportunity to rehabilitate themselves. However, following the invasion of the Warsaw Pact troops in August 1968, these hopes were dashed. K 231 was repealed, and although the rehabilitation law came into force, further amendments significantly complicated the possibility of rehabilitation.² This silenced the voices of the imprisoned and persecuted people of the 1950s for a long time.

However, the events of 17 November 1989 in Prague brought hope back to the lives of former political prisoners, some of whom became active participants in the revolution. Within the first few months, they established a new organization

¹ On the history of the K 231 organization, see HOPPE, Jiří: *Opozice '68: Sociální demokracie, KAN a K 231 v období pražského jara*. Praha, Prostor 2010; BLAŽEK, Petr – BURSÍK, Tomáš – HALLA, Josef – HOPPE, Jiří: *Aby se to už neopakovalo: Katalog k výstavě o dějinách Sdružení bývalých politických vězňů K-231*. Praha, Ústav pro studium totalitních režimů 2008.

² For more on the 1968 rehabilitation, see BURSÍK, Tomáš – PAŽOUT, Jaroslav (eds.): *Revize politických procesů a rehabilitace jejich obětí v komunistickém Československu: Mezinárodní, vnitropolitické, právní a společenské aspekty*. Praha, Ústav pro studium totalitních režimů 2021.

called the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia (*Konfederace politických vězňů Československa, KPVČ*). In a relatively short period of time, this organization grew to develop branches in several regions and attract a significant number of members. The members were interested not only in promoting improved conditions for former political prisoners and their rehabilitation, but also in becoming an important partner in ongoing political developments. The moral authority that the Confederation publicly promoted in various statements and memoranda from the outset of the revolution served as a significant driving force in the post-revolutionary process.

The Confederation has undertaken many activities since it was established, and in this article, we will examine mainly the early period, when it faced challenges from outside and within, including how it grew and formed its identity, and how involved it was in politics. While the Confederation built on the organization known as K 231, the conditions under which it operated and the scope of its activities differed considerably. This article will examine how these political, social and economic conditions influenced the Confederation's demands and strategies. It will emphasize the Confederation's political ambitions, examining not only its role in political struggles but also its ability to influence the national political agenda. Although the Confederation of Political Prisoners presented itself as non-political, its activities in the early 1990s heavily influenced political decisions. Seeing itself as a "mirror of the nation", it sought to promote its ideas about politics and democracy, often cooperating with various political entities. This text will analyse the contradiction between the Confederation's declared apolitical stance and its actual political engagement.

I view the development of the Confederation as part of the broader process of establishing civil society and democratic institutions in post-communist Czechoslovakia. Established during an extremely turbulent period, it managed to bring together a large number of members with diverse opinions and experiences in a short period of time. This inevitably led to organizational difficulties and internal conflicts. The final part of the article will therefore focus on the organization's internal dynamics, its efforts at moral cleansing, and the resulting conflicts.

The Confederation's activities in the early years of its existence were extremely broad, but this article will focus only on a select portion of them. The organization played a significant role in legislative processes relating to rehabilitation, compensation, lustration and the recognition of anti-communist resistance. It also actively organized memorial and commemorative events to honour the courage and heroism of political prisoners, as well as their suffering. The organization also sought to promote a retributive agenda and initiate legal proceedings against a number of former guards and investigators. However, these activities remain rather marginal in this text.

Although the original name was the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia, this designation can be considered somewhat misleading. The Slovak former political prisoners rejected the idea of a unified national organization, instead preferring a model of two confederated associations. Consequently, the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Slovakia (*Konfederácia politických väzňov Slovenska*, KPVS) was formed in Slovakia.³

Significantly, the archives of the Confederation of Political Prisoners held in the National Archives (*Národní archiv*) in Prague contain minimal material that could help reconstruct in more detail the Slovak part of the organization's functioning, the number of its branches, and the nature of Czech-Slovak cooperation among political prisoners. The magazine *Věrní zůstali* [Faithful They Remained], published by the Czech Confederation since 1991, contains no contributions from Slovak members, and the issue of Slovak political prisoners received no substantial reflection in the presidium's proceedings either. Cooperation between the two organizations therefore appears to have been very limited. For this reason, this text does not examine the Slovak organization or its potentially different goals and activities in detail. In the following discussion, the term "Confederation" refers exclusively to the Czech organization and its branches in what is now the Czech Republic.

Establishment of the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia

In the first week of the Velvet Revolution, a small group of former political prisoners met at the *Laterna Magica* theatre in Prague with representatives of the Civic Forum (*Občanské fórum*, OF), a political movement that emerged as a spontaneous platform for independent civic activity and negotiated with Communist Party officials to hand over power. The former political prisoners presented them with the "Declaration of the Political Prisoners of the 1950s".⁴ According to the

³ The preparatory committee consisted of Eugen Korda, Juraj Svoreň, Anton Tomík, Štefan Novák, Lubomír Danko, and Pavol Cintavý. At the first KPVS congress, held on 31 March 1990, Július Porubský was elected to lead the organization. (O nás. In: *Politický vězni - Zvaz protikomunistického odboja* [online]. [Accessed 2025-10-06.] Available at: <https://www.pvzpk.sk/o-nas/>.)

⁴ Prohlášení politických vězňů padesátých let. In: *České slovo*, Vol. 35, No. 12 (1989), p. 4. [Accessed 2025-10-06.] Available online at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/ceske-slovo/ceske-slovo_1989_12_ocr.pdf. *České slovo* was the exile newspaper edited monthly in Munich in 1955–1990.

recollections of former political prisoner Vladimír Struska,⁵ this declaration was broadcast by Radio Free Europe and later by the Voice of America: “We, the political prisoners of the 1950s, who from the start fought for free democracy and a free Czechoslovakia, support the demands of the nation for an investigation, publication and punishment of the terrorist order that led to the brutal intervention of the Interior Ministry forces against the peaceful demonstration of students on 17 November 1989. We demand a change in the political climate in the name of the 148 innocently executed and 8,000 martyred prisoners of the past forty years of this anti-people regime. We have known ‘communist humanism’ for a decade or more behind the barbed wire of concentration camps and the bars of infamous prisons throughout our country. We stand in full solidarity with every honest Czech and Slovak who wishes for the restoration of a free Czechoslovakia! Don’t be afraid! We weren’t afraid either! The truth will come out!”⁶

Some days later, on 30 November 1989, approximately thirty former political prisoners gathered at a Prague restaurant named U Kotvy, located in Spálená Street, for a meeting where they discussed the establishment of a new organization, the objectives it would pursue, and the direction it would take. The initial objective was that the membership of the organization would include individuals imprisoned during the 1950s as well as during the period of so-called normalization (1970s–1980s). The political prisoners of the normalization period – referred to here as dissidents – had not been tried under the controversial Law No. 231/1948 for the Protection of the People’s Democratic Republic. This law was used in the 1950s to convict actual or alleged opponents of the communist dictatorship, and it was from this law that the first organization derived its name.⁷ Since the

⁵ Vladimír Struska (1925–2000), active in the anti-communist resistance, took part in student anti-communist demonstrations in February 1948 and worked within the Prague-Žatec resistance organization. Arrested in 1949, he received a life sentence. In 1960, he was released under amnesty. During the Prague Spring in 1968, he became a founding member of Club 231. In 1990, he co-founded the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia. He played an active role in the Czech National Council (*Česká národní rada*) and in the establishment of the Museum of the Third Resistance (*Muzeum třetího odboje*) in Příbram. From 1992 to 2000, he served as secretary of the Czech branch of the Pan-European Union. (Struska, Vladimír, 1925–2000. In: *Středočeská knihovna v Kladně* [online]. [Accessed 2025-12-04.] Available at: https://ipac.svkk1.cz/ar1-kl/cs/detail-kl_us_auth-p0097365-Struska-Vladimir-19252000/.)

⁶ Prohlášení politických vězňů padesátých let (all translations from the Czech are by the author); STRUSKA, Vladimír: Založení KPV ČR. In: *Zpravodaj KPV ČR*, Vol. 1, No. 6 (1994), p. 2; PROKEŠOVÁ, Tereza: *Konfederace politických vězňů: Pobočka č. 19, Chudim* [online]. Pardubice, Filozofická fakulta Univerzity Pardubice 2009. Masters dissertation. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: <https://theses.cz/id/qszfc6/>, p. 46.

⁷ Zákon č. 231/1948 Sb.: Zákon na ochranu lidově demokratické republiky. In: *Zákony pro lidi* [online]. [Accessed 2025-12-04.] Available at: <https://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/1948-231>.

name of the 1968 organization “Club 231” referred to that law and would therefore exclude individuals imprisoned later, it was decided that the new organization would be called the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia.⁸

A few days later, an application for registration was drafted and on 18 December, a “Charter of Incorporation” followed, in which they declared their heritage and legal continuity with the K 231. The main declared aim of this new organization was to gather, preserve and publish the testimonies of persons subjected to various types of persecution between 1948 and 1989. The organization’s objectives also included advocating for comprehensive rehabilitation – legal and social – and addressing the health and social needs of former political prisoners, particularly in terms of access to medical and rehabilitation care and improved pensions.⁹ The formulation of these demands was undoubtedly influenced by the benefits previously granted to participants in the First and Second Resistance by the State.¹⁰

In the initial stages of the Confederation, a group of seventeen individuals were elected to the preparatory committee.¹¹ Although subsequent documentation predominantly references individuals who were imprisoned during the 1950s, including František Melichar, Čeněk Sovák, Vladimír Struska, Hilda Hojerová-Čiháková and Jitka Pufflerová-Rybáková,¹² it is important to note that in the early days of the Confederation, dissidents such as Václav Benda, Anna Šabatová, Ivan

⁸ JIRÁSEK, Ladislav: Tři roky Konfederace politických vězňů. In: *Věrní zůstali: Zpravodaj Konfederace politických vězňů* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 10 (1992), p. 1. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptorum.cz/scriptorum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_10_ocr.pdf; *Národní archiv* [The National Archives of the Czech Republic], Prague (hereafter *NA*), fond [collection] (hereafter *coll.*) Konfederace politických vězňů (hereafter *KPV*), karton [box] 6, untitled and undated document describing the founding of the KPV; *ibidem*, box 50, Pět let Konfederace politických vězňů [Five Years of the Confederation of Political Prisoners], undated.

⁹ *NA*, coll. *KPV*, box 128, Konfederace politických vězňů: Zakládací listina [Confederation of Political Prisoners: Founding Charter], 18. 12. 1989.

¹⁰ The Czech historical narrative is predominantly characterized by the persistent struggle for the survival of the Czechoslovak state. It is therefore evident that the annals of Czechoslovak history refer to two distinct forms of resistance activities. The First Resistance is widely regarded as pivotal in laying the foundations for the establishment of the Czechoslovak Republic during the First World War. The Second Resistance is understood as a movement engaged in the defence of the Czechoslovak state against Nazi Germany.

¹¹ The members of the preparatory committee were Václav Benda, Egon Čierny, Ivan Dejmal, Jan Dostál, Václav Findejs, Hilda Hojerová-Čiháková, Karel Macháček, František Melichar, Pavel Muraško, Čeněk Novák, Jitka Pufflerová-Rybáková, Roman Sakmar, Vladimír Struska, Anna Šabatová, Petr Uhl, Lili Uhlířová-Ričicová, and Dara Zuklínová-Zemanová.

¹² See for example *NA*, coll. *KPV*, box 6, untitled and undated document describing the founding of the KPV.

Dejmal, Petr Uhl and others also took part. References to the formation of this organization were published in the Czechoslovak samizdat magazine *Informace o Chartě 77*, or *Infoch 77* for short.¹³ The influence of the dissidents, visible in the text of the “Charter of Incorporation”, began to fade in the following weeks and political prisoners from the 1950s increasingly assumed the leading role.

The reason for the dissidents’ departure was probably not only the different views on the organization’s goals of decommunization, but also the question of who could be a member.¹⁴ The political prisoners of the 1950s adopted a more radical stance. While the “Charter of Incorporation” and the initial “Statutes of the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia” of 1990 stipulated that individuals who had been imprisoned for political reasons were eligible for membership, with only the vague restriction that they must have demonstrated ethical behaviour both during their imprisonment and afterwards,¹⁵ and not have engaged in activities that suppressed human rights,¹⁶ the Statutes a year later directly stipulated that no one who had been a member of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia (*Komunistická strana Československa*, KSČ) or had co-operated with the State Security (*Státní bezpečnost*, StB) could be a member.¹⁷ This condition excluded some dissidents who had been part of the communist establishment in their youth. However, this does not imply that there were no Communist Party members among the political prisoners from the 1950s. In fact, many of them concealed their Party membership – a fact that later caused some major internal strife.

¹³ *Infoch 77* was published as samizdat from 1978 to 1989, with three special issues appearing in 1990, 1991 and 1992. The publication primarily served as a medium for disseminating information about the activities of the Czechoslovak dissenting movement and the subsequent persecution of its members by the communist regime. In addition, it included a selection of reviews and essays. Several articles on the formation of the organization of political prisoners were published in *Infoch 77*, among them: [ANONYMOUS:] Výzva politickým vězňům. In: *Informace o Chartě 77* [online], Vol. 12, No. 22 (1989), p. 2. [Accessed 2025-02-12.] Available at: https://www.vons.cz/data/pdf/infoch/INFOCH_22_1989.pdf; [ANONYMOUS:] Zasedání politických vězňů. In: *Ibidem* [online], Vol. 13, No. 1 (1990), p. 10. [Accessed 2025-02-12.] Available at: https://www.vons.cz/data/pdf/infoch/INFOCH_01_1990.pdf.

¹⁴ BLAŽEK, Petr – BURSÍK, Tomáš: „Aby se to už neopakovalo“: Výstava o dějinách K 231 – Sdružení bývalých politických vězňů, panel 14: Bývalí političtí vězni po pádu železné opony [online]. [Accessed 2025-02-12.] Available at: <https://www.ustrcr.cz/data/pdf/k231/panel14.pdf>.

¹⁵ NA, coll. KPV, box 128, Konfederace politických vězňů. Zakládací listina, 18. 12. 1989.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, box 6, Stanovy Konfederace politických vězňů Československa [Statutes of the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia], 1990.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, box 128, Stanovy Konfederace politických vězňů Československa [Statutes of the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia], September 1991.

The available archival sources do not provide information on when the dissidents left the ranks of the Confederation founders.¹⁸ However, the break with them and their ideas is already apparent in the text of the “Memorandum of the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia”, which was signed on 1 February 1990. The language of human rights as articulated in the “Charter of Incorporation” gave way to an uncompromising stance towards the communist dictatorship, while the Confederation simultaneously affirmed the legacy of the Third (anti-communist) Resistance, which it sought to promote at the legal, historical and social levels in the ensuing years: “We are convinced that the preservation of freedom and democracy must be constantly sought, and we regard it as self-evident that citizens have the moral right and duty to resist by all means the arbitrary will of any power that has deprived them of these won freedoms. The prisoners of the 1950s were therefore the first to resist the takeover of power by the Communist Party. They – if they survived – and their families faced permanent persecution even after their release from prison. They can therefore rightly be seen as continuing the struggle for freedom and the defence of democracy in the same spirit as those who fought during the Second World War. It is not only among the prisoners that there is a belief that the period of unrestricted rule by the Communist Party constitutes the Third Resistance, since relatively most of those who were tried, executed, or otherwise affected were members of our national resistance during the Second World War. No nation has so unforgivably ‘repaid’ those who fought to regain its freedom.”¹⁹

On 18 February 1990, the Central Committee organized a general meeting at the Congress Palace in Prague, which was attended by approximately 5,000 former political prisoners, including representatives of the Czech National Council and various ministries.²⁰ A thirty-one-member committee, including a working bureau, was elected. The chairman was Rudolf Pernický,²¹ a representative of the Second Resistance, who had been sentenced to twenty years’ imprisonment in a show

¹⁸ The Council of the Confederation that emerged from the September 1991 elections does not include any of the dissidents who were also founding members.

¹⁹ NA, coll. KPV, box 6, Memorandum, 1. 2. 1990.

²⁰ The Czech National Council (*Česká národní rada*, ČNR) was the legislative body of the Czech Socialist Republic, later the Czech Republic, from 1 January 1969 to 31 December 1992.

²¹ Rudolf Pernický (1915–2005), Czechoslovak soldier, paratrooper and political prisoner. During the Second World War he served in the foreign army and commanded the Tungsten Airborne. After the communist coup in February 1948, he was arrested and sentenced to twenty years in prison, spending over ten years in harsh prisons and uranium camps. He was released by amnesty in 1960, after which he could only work manually and remained under StB surveillance. After 1989, he was rehabilitated, promoted to the rank of major general and became one of the founders and the first chairman of the Confederation of Political Prisoners.

trial in 1949, and the first executive chairman was Vladimír Struska, a member of the so-called Prague-Žatec resistance group,²² who had been sentenced to life imprisonment. The former dissident and later President of the Republic Václav Havel was elected honorary chairman.²³ The whole effort culminated in success on 13 March, when the Confederation was registered with the Federal Ministry of the Interior.²⁴ The Confederation experienced a rapid increase in membership, with estimates suggesting that by 1990, it counted approximately 16,000 members.²⁵

Political prisoners were active not only in Prague. Enthusiasm spread in the regions as well, and the friendly relations that had developed among prisoners after their release led to the rapid creation of numerous branches, reaching nineteen by March 1990.²⁶ The Confederation continued to grow quickly, with the number of branches rising to eighty-two by October of that year.²⁷ For instance, in Nová Paka, northeastern Bohemia, the inaugural meeting to establish the organization took place in Vratislav Číla's apartment on 9 December 1989.²⁸ Subsequently, representatives attended a meeting in the Congress Palace and on 10 March 1990 the first constituent meeting was held, during which elections took place, a chairman (Vratislav Číla) was elected, and representatives of the individual commissions

²² For more see for example PLACHÝ, Jiří: Praha-Žatec a StB? In: *Paměť a dějiny*, Vol. 7, No. 1 (2013), pp. 47–55; PEJČOCH, Ivo: *Protikomunistické puče: Historie pokusů o vojenské svržení komunistického režimu v Československu v letech 1948 až 1958*. Cheb, Svět křídel 2011; IDEM: „Akce Praha – Žatec“: Údajný pokus o vojenský protikomunistický puč. In: *Historie a vojenství*, Vol. 59, No. 2 (2010), pp. 33–51; MALLOTA, Petr: Protikomunistická odbojová organizace Praha – Žatec: Konstrukce, provokace, či skutečnost? In: *Solitér: Pocta historikovi Václavu Veberovi*. Praha, Ústav pro studium totalitních režimů 2012, pp. 75–102.

²³ NA, coll. KPV, box 6, untitled and undated document describing the founding of the KPV.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, Rozhodnutí Federálního ministerstva vnitra č. j. OV-118/P-90 [Decision of the Federal Ministry of the Interior, ref. no. OV-118/P-90], 13. 3. 1990.

²⁵ BLAŽEK, P. – BURSÍK, T.: „Aby se to už neopakovalo“, panel 14: Bývalí političtí vězni po pádu železné opony [online].

²⁶ NA, coll. KPV, box 50, *Zpravodaj KPVC*, č. 1 [KPVC Newsletter No. 1], 20. 3. 1990.

²⁷ *Ibidem*, box 4, Výzva k založení „Čisté koalice“ [Call for the establishment of a “Clean Coalition”], undated, probably October 1990.

²⁸ Vratislav Číla (1929–2001) was a member of the resistance group led by General František Sluneček, operating under the codename “Alex”. Following the cessation of the Second World War, he was honoured for his contributions. After the communist coup, he joined the resistance activities led by Stanislav Maděra. Consequently, he was sentenced to twenty-two years’ imprisonment in 1950. Following his release on parole in 1960, he remained under house arrest. In 1977, he became a signatory of Charter 77, a significant act that drew international attention and support for his cause. After November 1989, he led the KPV branch in Nová Paka.

were appointed. In July 1990 the branch had 107 registered members.²⁹ One of the first district branches to form was the branch in Chrudim, Eastern Bohemia, headed by Zdeněk Dušek, which had 244 members at its founding.³⁰ Branches of the Confederation also emerged in Slovakia.

The Confederation as the Bearer and Guardian of the Legacy of the Victims of Communist Terror

Since its inception, the Confederation had confronted two fundamental challenges: firstly, the necessity of establishing its organizational structure and *modus operandi*; and secondly, the imperative to articulate its objectives, ideals and aspirations to the general public. While in the early 1990s its primary objectives still centred on improving the living conditions of its members, rehabilitating and compensating them, promoting social and health benefits, and collecting and publishing documentation of human rights violations,³¹ the following months of political change radicalized its ideas. These emerged in the form of demands for rigorous decommunization, coupled with lustration and the exclusion of all former Communist Party members from leadership positions in public life, the criminalization and judicial punishment of perpetrators responsible for violence and persecution, and the promotion of legal recognition of the anti-communist resistance.³² The Confederation, in conjunction with other organizations of a similar ideological disposition, including the Movement for Civil Liberties (*Hnutí za občanskou svobodu*, HOS) and the Club of Committed Non-Party Members (*Klub angažovaných nestraníků*, KAN), developed into one of the radical and anti-communist currents that coalesced into the post-dissident movement.³³

The objective of the Confederation, which defined itself as a non-political movement, was to influence the prevailing political situation. During 1990, the Confederation's objectives gained momentum, driven by growing disillusionment with the "thick-line-behind-the-past" policy espoused by President Václav Havel and by a mounting sense of disrespect. From their perspective, the media as

²⁹ NA, coll. KPV, box 134, Činnost Okresní pobočky nejprve K 231 a potom KPVČ [Activities of the District Branch of the K 231, later KPVČ], Nová Paka, undated, probably 1994.

³⁰ PROKEŠOVÁ, T.: *Konfederace politických vězňů* [online], p. 52.

³¹ NA, coll. KPV, box 6, Stanovy Konfederace politických vězňů Československa, 1990.

³² *Ibidem*, box 128, Stanovy Konfederace politických vězňů Československa, September 1991.

³³ SUK, Jiří: Anatomy of the End of Charter 77 (1990–1992): Between Politics, Morality, Business and Coming to Terms with the Past. In: *Soudobé dějiny / Czech Journal of Contemporary History*, Vol. 31, No. 3 (2024), pp. 673–717, here p. 678.

well as the general public failed to acknowledge their historical contributions to the collapse of the communist dictatorship. They viewed the credit given to the “sixty-eighters” (*osmašedesátníci* in Czech – i.e. active participants in the social and political events of 1968 who became dissidents in the 1970s and 1980s) as a misstep. Feelings of frustration – undoubtedly linked to the long psychosocial development of the group of political prisoners before 1989, the aftermath of unprocessed trauma and the group’s constructed sense of exceptionalism as early fighters against communism – led them to see themselves in terms of morality, honour and suffering.³⁴ They believed that their suffering and years in prison had predisposed them to stand at the forefront of the political scene.³⁵

In the period following the revolution, there were discussions about how to influence political developments. One option under consideration was the establishment of a political party uniting victims of communist oppression.³⁶ However, these discussions took place mainly in the first two post-revolutionary years. During the 1990s, concern among political prisoners grew that the political power of the Communist Party was rising again. They believed they needed to speak out more strongly against it and to warn of the danger of a return to communism. The establishment of a political party was eventually rejected in favour of what the political prisoners saw as the primary function of the Confederation: surveillance, protection, and warning. The victims of the communist dictatorship were cognisant of both their advanced age and the heterogeneity of their political convictions and opinions. Despite this, what bound them together was their common hostility to communism and their shared experience of imprisonment. They recognized that this was insufficient for the successful functioning of a political party. Furthermore, several political prisoners had previously belonged to various political parties and movements before their arrest, and in some cases even after 1989. In the aftermath of the Velvet Revolution, many of them rejoined these political groups, and if the Confederation had been established as a political party, they would have faced the dilemma of deciding which political party to prefer.³⁷

³⁴ MAYER, Françoise: *Češi a jejich komunismus: Paměť a politická identita*. Praha, Argo 2009, pp. 171–174; EADEM: *Vězení jako minulost, odboj jako paměť: Konfederace politických vězňů*. In: *Soudobé dějiny*, Vol. 9, No. 1 (2002), pp. 47–49; PINEROVÁ, Klára: *Do konce života: Političtí vězni padesátých let – trauma, adaptace, identita*. Praha, Ústav pro studium totalitních režimů – Nakladatelství Lidové noviny 2017, p. 302.

³⁵ FINDEJS, Václav: *Založení politické komise KPVČ*. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 1.] No. 4 (1991), p. 2. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: http://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1991_04_ocr.pdf.

³⁶ MAYER, F.: *Češi a jejich komunismus*, p. 179.

³⁷ NA, coll. KPV, box 41, *Návrh na ustavení politické komise Konfederace* [Proposal to Establish a Political Commission of the Confederation], 6. 10. 1990.

In the autumn of 1990, the leadership of the Confederation defined its role as “the bearer and guardian of the legacy of the victims of communist terror”.³⁸ This definition entailed various challenges, including the decision to adopt an internal structure that restricted membership to individuals with direct experience of imprisonment or their family members. As time passed, the Statutes grew increasingly specific in delineating who could not be a member – a situation caused by internal struggles and disputes over the “purity” of the organization, a topic that will be addressed subsequently. The notion of an organization composed exclusively of “morally upright members” emerged from the long evolution of the political prisoners’ identity. After their release, they had become politically and narratively polarized and tended to regard themselves uncritically as the “conscience” or “mirror of the nation”. The idea of establishing the Confederation as a political entity raised concerns that its “moral credit” might be undermined by offering membership to individuals without this shared experience. This would, they feared, result in the loss of their distinctive stance against the communist dictatorship.³⁹ This close-mindedness later deepened the polarization among political prisoners, reinforced their rigid definition of everything “communist”, intensified their rejection of any conciliatory attitude, and heightened their sense of threat, which re-traumatized them. Years later, this rigid stance within the organization fostered fears that the legacy of the Confederation and the memory of political prisoners would die along with them.⁴⁰

Political Ambition vs. Moral Mission: Debates on the Future of the Confederation

The Confederation of Political Prisoners did not enter the political fray as a political party with an anti-communist right-wing programme. Some leaders in the later period, such as the second chairman Stanislav Drobný,⁴¹ criticized this decision, arguing that it failed to give the Confederation sufficient influence on the

³⁸ *Ibidem.*

³⁹ *Ibidem.*

⁴⁰ KÁJÍNEK, Milan: Roztržka mezi politickými vězni: Organizace zemře spolu s námi... – Ne, mohou pokračovat naše děti a vnuci! In: *Epoch Times* [online], 02. 09. 2019. [Accessed 2025-02-18.] Available at: <https://www.epochtimes.cz/2019/09/02/roztrzka-mezi-politickymi-vezni-organizace-zemre-spolu-s-nami-ne-mohou-pokracovat-nase-deti-a-jejich-deti/>.

⁴¹ Stanislav Drobný (1923–2013) initially trained as a lawyer. In 1949, he was convicted of treason and sentenced to thirteen years’ imprisonment. He was freed in 1962. After his release, he worked as an electrician until his retirement. Since 1990, he had been involved in the Confederation of Political Prisoners. His involvement began with his appointment as

political scene.⁴² In the early 1990s, Confederation leaders sought ways to steer various political decisions in their favour. They did not significantly engage in the political discussions within the Civic Forum. From the spring of 1990, voices of warning began to rise from various quarters that former Communists were regaining power. In his speech on the 22nd anniversary of the Soviet-led 1968 occupation – which ended the period of the so-called Prague Spring, a time of attempted reform and liberalization – President Václav Havel spoke of “invisible mafias” that had created a “dangerous jungle”.⁴³ During this period, the Confederation decided to take an active role in public discourse, recognizing the necessity of communicating not only with political leaders but also the general public. To this end, they sought to influence public opinion through media appearances, newspaper articles, and rallies organized in collaboration with like-minded organizations. A notable example of this collaborative effort was the “Manifestation of all MUKLs from all over the world” (*manifestace všech muklů z celého světa*) on 12 May 1990 in Wenceslas Square in Prague.⁴⁴ This event, organized by the Confederation, the KAN, the HOS, the Union of Auxiliary Technical Battalions (*Svaz Pomocných technických praporů*),⁴⁵ and a segment of the Civic Forum, drew several thousand participants.⁴⁶ A few months later, they also helped organize

chairman of the Brno branch, and he subsequently served as chairman of the Confederation from 1991 to 2003.

⁴² HALLA, Josef: *Organizace bývalých politických vězňů: Klub K-231 v exilu (1985–1990)* [online]. Brno, Historický ústav, Filozofická fakulta Masarykovy univerzity 2001, p. 98. Masters dissertation. [Accessed 2025-02-14.] Available at: <https://is.muni.cz/th/anhtg/text.pdcoll>.

⁴³ HAVEL, Václav: Výročí okupace Československa vojsky zemí Varšavského paktu: Projev, 21. 8. 1990. In: IDEM: *Projevy z let 1990–1992; Letní přemítání*. (Spisy, sv. 6.) Ed. Jan Zelenka. Praha, Torst 1999, pp. 234–248. See SUK, J.: Anatomy of the End of Charter 77, p. 685.

⁴⁴ MUKL – an abbreviation popularly interpreted as “man destined for liquidation” (*muž určený k likvidaci*) or “man oppressed by the communist mob” (*muž utlačovaný komunistickou lůzou*). In the Czechoslovak context, it is mainly used to refer to political prisoners of the communist regime, especially from the 1950s. However, the claim that this term served as an official secret abbreviation with the above meaning is not reliably documented. In fact, this interpretation was popularized during the Prague Spring of 1968 by the political prisoners themselves, who sought to draw attention to the hardships they had experienced in the 1950s.

⁴⁵ The Union of Auxiliary Technical Battalions (*Svaz PTP*) was founded in May 1968 but ceased its activities after the invasion of Warsaw Pact troops later that year. It was re-established in February 1990. It brought together men who were assigned to these units within the Czechoslovak Army between 1950 and 1954 because they were considered politically suspect and unreliable. Widows were also represented in the union. The union ceased its activities in 2016.

⁴⁶ HALLA, J.: *Organizace bývalých politických vězňů* [online], p. 94; NA, coll. KPV, box 50, *Zpravodaj KPVC*, č. 1, undated.

a rally on the anniversary of the invasion of the Warsaw Pact troops, entitled “August and the Communist Party” (*Srpen a komunistická strana*).⁴⁷ At these rallies, they promoted the ideas of rehabilitation, consistent decommunization, and the concept of anti-communist resistance.⁴⁸

But the Confederation’s representatives’ main goal at this time was to enter the political decision-making process, because they believed that their resistance to communism and the suffering they had endured gave them the right to serve as the “moral compass” for the future political direction of Czechoslovakia. However, as a non-political organization, its possibilities were limited. One way of influencing events on the political scene was through its members, who successfully stood for election to the Federal Assembly (*Federální shromáždění*) in the June 1990 elections. However, age and political inexperience proved to be major limitations. One of the successful candidates was Bohuslav Hubálek (1933–2017),⁴⁹ who served in the Federal Assembly until 1992, during which time he attempted to advance some of the laws promoted by the Confederation. He was the only who cooperated with the Confederation in a significant way.

In order to better promote its goals, the Confederation created, in addition to the traditional bodies such as the Central Committee (renamed Council in 1991), the Presidium and the General Assembly, several commissions with different responsibilities and mandates. Their creation was undoubtedly inspired by the existence of similar commissions in the K 231 organization, and their number changed gradually. The following committees were established: Legal; Social Welfare and Health; Defence and Security; Organization and Coordination; Agricultural; Documentation; and Political. The existence of these commissions was enshrined in the Statutes in 1990. However, most of them did not begin operating until the second half of the 1990s. One of the reasons for creating the Political Commission was the perceived need for greater involvement of the Confederation of Political Prisoners in political life. A proposal to establish this commission – intended to have eight to fifteen members and to be responsible for developing concepts and positions and directing the Confederation’s political activities – was introduced on 6 October 1990. Its members would be responsible for the systematic analysis of the domestic political situation and for co-operation with political parties and other associations.

⁴⁷ SUK, Jiří: Politické hry s „nedokončenou revolucí“: Účtování s komunismem v čase Občanského fóra a po jeho rozpadu (1989–1992). In: *Soudobé dějiny*, Vol. 16, No. 2–3 (2009), pp. 276–312, here p. 302.

⁴⁸ NA, coll. KPV, box 4, Provolání [Proclamation], 12. 5. 1990.

⁴⁹ Bohuslav Hubálek. In: *Poslanecká sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky* [online]. [Accessed 2025-02-14.] Available at: <https://www.psp.cz/sqw/detail.sqw?org=258&id=1672&l=cz>.

It is clear from the draft that during this period the Confederation's leaders struggled with a persistent sense of threat posed by the Communist Party's potential return to power. According to the proposal, this commission was supposed to prevent "totalitarianism from re-emerging" in the event of a "political crisis". Čestmír Čejka, Bohuslav Hubálek, Jiří Mesicki, Vladimír Struska, Roman Sakmar, Čeněk Sovák and Miroslav Dolejší⁵⁰ were among those recommended for appointment to this commission.⁵¹ At the beginning, however, the commission's activity remained limited, and it is likely it did not meet in the months that followed. It was not until 20 July 1991 that a preparatory meeting took place, and less than a month later representatives of the Confederation's branches met and established the Committee of the Political Commission.⁵² Bohuslav Hubálek became chairman of the Committee on 21 September 1991.⁵³

Since its establishment in 1990, the Commission's goals of lustration and decommunization intensified in response to domestic and international political events. According to one of the Commission's members, Václav Findejs, the Commission intended to pressure the state leadership to remove past and present members of the Communist Party from leading positions. They even wanted

⁵⁰ Miroslav Dolejší (1931–2001) was a political prisoner, dissident, and publicist. In 1951 he was arrested and sentenced to twenty-three years in prison for treason and espionage, spending nearly nineteen years in harsh prisons and uranium camps. After his release, he worked as a labourer and later became involved in the dissident milieu. After 1989, he published the controversial text *Analyza 17. listopadu* [Analysis of 17 November 1989], in which he interpreted the fall of the regime as a negotiated transfer of power between the communist structures and selected opposition elites (DOLEJŠÍ, Miroslav: *Analyza 17. listopadu*. Locket nad Ohří, C & B Agentura 1990).

⁵¹ NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Návrh na ustanovení politické komise Konfederace [Proposal to Establish a Political Commission of the Confederation], 6. 10. 1990; *ibidem*, box 136, Návrh na ustanovení politické komise Konfederace [Proposal to Establish a Political Commission of the Confederation], 30. 10. 1990; *ibidem*, box 4, Zápis z rozšířeného výboru Konfederace politických vězňů [Minutes of the Extended Committee Meeting of the Confederation of Political Prisoners], 10. 10. 1990.

⁵² *Ibidem*, box 4, Letter from Václav Findejs to KPVČ branches, 20. 7. 1991; FINDEJS, Václav: Založení politické komise KPVČ [online]. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 1.] No. 4 (1991), p. 2. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1991_04_ocr.pdf; NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Výroční zpráva o činnosti politické komise KPVČ v roce 1991 [Annual Report on the Activities of the KPVČ Political Commission in 1991], undated.

⁵³ NA, coll. KPV, box 6, Předsednictvo Rady KPVČ [Presidium of the KPVČ Council], 21. 9. 1991. He was succeeded by Jiří Mesicki in 1992 (*ibidem*, box 41, Minutes of the KPVČ Council meeting, 17. 6. 1992).

to set up control bodies that would “oversee the appointment of key staff in politics and the economy”.⁵⁴

There was another important aspect to the second half of 1991 for the Confederation. In connection with the aim of having a “morally upright organization”, heated discussions arose about the presence of State Security collaborators in the leadership and among the members. As a result, an extraordinary general meeting took place in September, which brought a change in the Confederation’s leadership. Rudolf Pernický was replaced as chairman by Stanislav Drobný, who introduced new energy into the organization. Drobný, who had spent thirteen years in prison, first became active in the Confederation as chairman of the Brno branch.⁵⁵ In Brno, he took part in the Civic Forum disputes between former dissidents Jaroslav Šabata and Petr Cibulka over whether the communist politician Josef Pernica should remain mayor of Brno in 1990.⁵⁶

But the election of a new Council was not the only change. In August 1991, a coup attempt in the Soviet Union triggered a radicalization of public opinion in Czechoslovakia.⁵⁷ Political prisoners responded by adopting a more activist stance and seeking to become involved in the upcoming 1992 elections.⁵⁸ Efforts to secure successful candidacies were not left solely to the personal initiative of individual members; the leadership also attempted in various ways to enter political negotiations, with the support of branch representatives at a meeting in Harrachov, Northern Bohemia, in early November.⁵⁹ They tried to enter the political arena without becoming a political party and engaged in several negotiations.

⁵⁴ FINDEJS, Václav: Založení politické komise KPVČ. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 1.] No. 4 (1991), p. 2. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1991_04_ocr.pdf; srv. NA, coll. KPV, box 4, Poslání politické komise, její organizace [Mission of the Political Commission, Its Organization], undated, probably 1991; *ibidem*, Programové prohlášení politické komise Konfederace politických vězňů Československa [Programme Statement of the KPVČ Political Commission], undated, probably 1991.

⁵⁵ DROBNÝ, Tomáš: Vzpomínky na tatínka. In: *Skleněný kostel* [online], 13. 01. 2014. [Accessed 2025-02-20.] Available at: <http://www.sklenenykostel.net/index.php/menu-hist/2894-a-18-3183>.

⁵⁶ See SUK, Jiří: *Labyrintem revoluce: Aktéři, zápletky a křížovatky jedné politické krize*. Praha, Prostor 2020; GOLASOWSKI, Pavel: *Antikomunismus v české polistopadové politice: Případ Šabata kontra Cibulka* [online]. Brno, Katedra politologie, Fakulta sociálních studií Masarykovy univerzity 2011, p. 28. Bachelors dissertation. [Accessed 2025-02-12.] Available at: https://is.muni.cz/th/n615m/Bakalarska_Prace_-_Golasowski_Pavel.pdcoll.

⁵⁷ SUK, J.: Anatomy of the End of Charter 77, p. 686.

⁵⁸ NA, coll. KPV, box 4, Prohlášení KAN, KDP, KPVČ a Svazu PTP [Statement by the KAN, KDP, KPVČ, and Svaz PTP], 16. 8. 1991.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, box 41, Setkání politických vězňů [Meeting of Political Prisoners], 1. 11. 1991.

On 10 September 1991, for example, Jiří Mesicki joined the preparatory committee of the Anti-Communist Alliance (*Antikomunistická aliance*), a civic initiative that called for the “purification of society” and the rehabilitation of victims. It supported radical economic reform and opposed interpreting the events of 1968 as an attempt at democratic change.⁶⁰ In the end, however, the Confederation did not participate in this alliance in any significant way.⁶¹

Another similar meeting took place in November in České Budějovice, Southern Bohemia, where representatives of the Christian and Democratic Union – Czechoslovak People’s Party (*Křesťanská a demokratická unie – Československá strana lidová*, KDÚ-ČSL), the KAN, the Christian Democratic Party (*Křesťanskodemokratická strana*, KDS), the Liberal Democratic Party (*Liberálně demokratická strana*, LDS), the Civic Democratic Party (*Občanská demokratická strana*, ODS), the Republican Union (*Republikánská unie*), the Association of Czechoslovak Businessmen (*Sdružení československých podnikatelů*) and the Confederation agreed on the need to create a “bloc of conservative forces”.⁶² In January of the following year, a member of the Political Commission, Václav Findejs, met with representatives of the KAN, the HOS, the National Social Party (*Národně sociální strana*), the Republican Union, the monarchist political party Czech Crown (*Koruna Česká – monarchistická strana Čech, Moravy a Slezska*), the Liberal Party (*Liberální strana*) and the Association of Social Democrats (*Asociace sociálních demokratů*) to discuss a possible coalition partnership. They agreed on the demand for recognition of the anti-communist resistance, “the de-Bolshevization of society and democratization”. The Confederation was offered a place in the coalition.⁶³

The efforts to join a conservative political association without formally becoming a political party were accompanied by negotiations with individual parties and associations about placing Confederation members on their lists of candidates.⁶⁴ The Confederation required these parties to support a right-wing programme, uphold the principles of complete decommunization, and exclude

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, Antikomunistická aliance [Anti-Communist Alliance], 10. 9. 1991.

⁶¹ *Ibidem*, Politická komise, zápis z jednání [Political Commission, Minutes of the Meeting], 9. 10. 1991.

⁶² *Ibidem*, Založení bloku konzervativně orientovaných sil v Č[eských] Budějovicích [Establishment of a Bloc of Conservative Forces in České Budějovice], 12. 11. 1991.

⁶³ *Ibidem*, Zpráva z jednání politické komise, V. Findejs [Report from the Meeting of the Political Commission, V. Findejs], 7. 1. 1992; *ibidem*, Setkání pravicových stran [Meeting of Right-wing Parties], undated, probably 1991.

⁶⁴ Rada KPV: Bratři a sestry. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 4 (1992), p. 5. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_04_ocr.pdf.

from their membership and candidate lists anyone historically linked to the Communist Party or to cooperation with the State Security.⁶⁵ However, not all parties possessed the capacity or inclination to adhere to these requirements. In the following years, this stipulation proved impossible to fulfil. Consequently, in the next electoral cycle, the Confederation adopted a different approach and no longer sought to promote its members as candidates.

During this period, contacts between the Confederation and the Civic Democratic Party intensified,⁶⁶ and at the turn of the millennium ODS emerged as an “ally and partner” of political prisoners. Since 2003 the third chairwoman, Naděžda Kavalírová,⁶⁷ regularly attended ODS congresses, where she delivered formal greetings.⁶⁸ However, the process leading to the establishment of this alliance was lengthy. In the early 1990s, the ODS promoted the notion that left-wing activists from the Civic Forum and former communists had joined the Civic Movement (*Občanské hnutí*, OH) after the dissolution of the Civic Forum in April 1991.⁶⁹ The Confederation accepted this interpretation and published a number of articles in their magazine, *Věrní zůstali*, which not only criticized the activities of the Civic Movement but also publicly disparaged individual representatives.⁷⁰ Despite ODS’s public stance against communism and communists, their subsequent actions did not fully correspond to this declared position.⁷¹ At the turn

⁶⁵ NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Minutes of the meeting of the KPVČ Political Commission, 2. 3. 1992.

⁶⁶ The ODS was founded at its constituent congress in April 1991, following the dissolution of the Civic Forum (OF). In November 1991, the ODS formed a coalition with the Christian Democratic Party (KDS). The ODS-KDS coalition won all legislative bodies in the summer 1992 elections.

⁶⁷ Naděžda Kavalírová, née Morávková (1923–2017), was the Confederation’s chairwoman from 2003 onward. In her youth, she was a member of the Czechoslovak National Socialist Party (*Československá strana národně socialistická*). From 1945 she studied medicine at the Medical Faculty of Charles University, from which she was expelled in March 1948 for being politically unreliable. In 1956 she was arrested and convicted in a sham trial for alleged treason and espionage. She was released in 1959. After her release, she held various manual positions, including work as an unskilled labourer and as a lathe operator, before becoming a clerk with the National Committee (*národní výbor*) in Prague 9. During the period of normalization, Kavalírová spent eighteen years as a clerk at the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs.

⁶⁸ GJURIČOVÁ, Adéla: Poněkud tradiční rozchod s minulostí: Přítomnost minulosti v ideologii a politické rétorice Občanské demokratické strany. In: *Soudobé dějiny*, Vol. 16, No. 2–3 (2009), pp. 313–332, here pp. 330–331.

⁶⁹ Ibidem, p. 321.

⁷⁰ Rada KPV: Bratři a sestry. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 4 (1992), p. 5. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_04_ocr.pdf.

⁷¹ GJURIČOVÁ, A.: Poněkud tradiční rozchod s minulostí, pp. 321–322.

of 1991 and 1992, Confederation members met several times with ODS representatives.⁷² In January 1992, Stanislav Drobný submitted a list of former political prisoners who were members of the ODS, with the intention of nominating them for election.⁷³ However, individual political prisoners highlighted the presence of numerous individuals with a communist background within the ODS membership, which discouraged the Confederation's leadership from pursuing further collaboration.⁷⁴ The accuracy of these concerns is substantiated by data from the ODS Executive Council, which had conducted an assessment of the proportion of former communists within the membership base prior to the elections. The findings revealed that the Prague branch recorded three percent, most regions five to ten percent, and the North Moravian region as much as nineteen percent.⁷⁵ Consequently, no former political prisoners ran for ODS, although the reasons for this remain uncertain. In the end, approximately forty-two political prisoners stood on the lists of various parties (KAN, National Social Party, KDS).⁷⁶

The organization and influence of the election results were significantly impacted by the Confederation's appeals to its members on how to vote. Members were instructed to follow the advice and decisions of the Confederation leadership, as they were believed to possess superior information: "Sisters and brothers, friends, this election is crucial to saving democracy in our country. It is your duty, sister and brother, to exert all your strength for the victory of the right-wing movement. Get rid of sentimental attachment to 'your' party, especially since, it has no hope of success and is a third way to communism. Orient yourself according to our recommendations, as we have more information at our headquarters."⁷⁷ According to a survey of Confederation members' sympathies conducted by the Political Commission, the majority of members expressed a preference for the ODS (26%) and the KAN (14%).⁷⁸

⁷² NA, coll. KPV, box 41, ODS - PK KPVČ: Informativní schůzka [ODS - PK KPVČ, Informative Meeting], 28. 11. 1991; *ibidem*, Letter from Stanislav Drobný to ODS, 21. 1. 1992.

⁷³ *Ibidem*.

⁷⁴ *Ibidem*, Politická komise KPVČ [KPVČ Political Commission], 20. 1. 1992.

⁷⁵ GJURIČOVÁ, A.: Poněkud tradiční rozchod s minulostí, pp. 322.

⁷⁶ [ANONYMOUS:] Kandidáti Konfederace politických vězňů. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2.] No. 5 (1992), p. 1. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_05_ocr.pdf.

⁷⁷ Political Commission of the KPV: [Untitled article]. In: *Ibidem* [online]. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_05_ocr.pdf.

⁷⁸ NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Politická komise KPVČ: Vyhodnocení průzkumu sympatií členů KPVČ k politickým stranám [KPVČ Political Commission: Evaluation of a Survey of KPVČ Members' Preferences for Political Parties], 10. 1. 1992.

The outcome of the election was a major disappointment for political prisoners, as none of the proposed candidates were elected to the Federal Assembly.⁷⁹ This disillusionment was widespread among the prisoners and was accompanied by a broader sense of frustration with the democratic development of Czechoslovakia. Indeed, some perceived the possible return of the communists to power as a threat. The extent to which these sentiments were shared among individual members remains uncertain; however, concerns about a potential left-wing coup were articulated during a meeting of the Confederation Council.⁸⁰ Some commentators drew parallels between the election results and the political situation in Czechoslovakia prior to the communist coup.⁸¹ The Confederation's subsequent desire to establish crisis staffs in each branch, with the aim of coordinating the activities of the headquarters and branches in the event of an emergency, such as a communist coup, illustrates the intensity of these perceived threats.⁸² While these staffs were indeed established in the organization's headquarters and in some branches, they were later dissolved.

Despite the bitterness over the election results, the political prisoners sought to portray themselves as moral winners by giving their votes to groups "not infested with communists and fascists". This is evident in the articles published in *Věrní zůstali*, where their choice was characterized as correct and guided by moral goals: "...to ensure the peace and security for our descendants, to consolidate the rule of law, to restore morality and faith in the nation, to de-bolshevize society, and to disarm the forces that disturb the harmony of the state."⁸³ The failure in the elections strengthened their messianic and moral self-image as a group that

⁷⁹ Redakce: Po volbách. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 8 (1992), pp. 1-2. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_08_ocr.pdf; NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Výroční zpráva o činnosti politické komise KPVČ v roce 1991 [Annual Report on the Activities of the KPVČ Political Commission in 1991], undated.

⁸⁰ NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Výzva Konfederace politických vězňů Československa [Appeal by the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia], 17. 6. 1992.

⁸¹ "As professional soldiers who correctly assessed the political developments in our country in 1948 and fulfilled our oath to defend freedom and democracy in our country, we expect our political leaders to take an uncompromising stance in the current era, which evokes the threats to the republic prior to February 1948." (Prohlášení vojenské sekce Konfederace. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 8 (1992), p. 2. [Accessed 2025-02-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_08_ocr.pdf.)

⁸² NA, coll. KPV, box 41, Minutes from the meeting of the KPVČ Political Commission, 22. 6. 1992.

⁸³ [ANONYMOUS:] Po volbách. In: *Věrní zůstali* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 8 (1992), pp. 1-2. [Accessed 2025-11-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_08_ocr.pdf.

had sacrificed itself for the well-being of others.⁸⁴ The perception of the group as a “marching conscience” was identified as a contributing factor to their failure, as this moralizing stance discouraged others from cooperating.⁸⁵

After the elections, the Confederation leadership abandoned the idea that they would be an equal force alongside political parties, and in the following period struggled to define their role on the political scene and in public life. This uncertainty regarding future direction was reflected not only at the meeting of the Confederation Council but also at the meeting of the Political Commission, which decided to address an array of disparate issues. The Commission adopted a multifaceted approach, disseminating letters and open letters to representatives of various political parties and ministries, highlighting personnel issues, and demanding redress. The Commission’s agenda encompassed topics ranging from the disintegration of Czechoslovakia and economic reforms to the establishment of memorial sites – such as the burial ground at the cemetery in Prague-Ďáblice or on Wenceslas Square – as well as more mundane matters, including the installation of telephones, the provision of recreational facilities for members, and the production of a wall calendar. Such an expansion of the Political Commission’s interests diluted the Confederation’s ability to promote its political visions for the future development of Czechoslovakia, and later the Czech Republic, particularly in the areas of decommunization and the desired banning or criminalization of the Communist Party. Moreover, this expansion was weakened by a series of personal disputes involving not only the “cleansing” of the organization of Communist Party members and State Security collaborators, but also internal power struggles. These conflicts paralysed the Confederation’s activities in the subsequent years.

Confederation between Cohesion and Conflict

In 1993, former political prisoner Jan Nesládek wrote: “God, what has happened to us? We, who were willing to place the most precious thing a person has – his life – on the scales for truth, freedom, and democracy, instead of demonstrating through our conduct that the whole nation needs rehabilitation far more than

⁸⁴ -om-: Okresní plenární schůze v Havířově. In: *Ibidem* [online], [Vol. 3,] No. 2 (1993), p. 5. [Accessed 2025-11-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1993_02_ocr.pdf.

⁸⁵ -s-: Výbor odmítl předsedovu rezignaci. In: *Ibidem* [online], [Vol. 2,] No. 10 (1992), p. 4. [Accessed 2025-11-28.] Available at: https://files.scriptum.cz/scriptum/verni-zustali-zustaneme/verni-zustali_1992_10_ocr.pdf.

we do, instead of pointing to those among our contemporaries for whom we serve as a reproach, instead of being able to dissociate ourselves from those who, after many years of imprisonment, could have signed up to cooperate with our executioners – we behave in a totally irresponsible manner, harassing, slandering and accusing one another, and even threatening each other with legal action.”⁸⁶ The narrative of sacrifice for the “greater good”, and the belief in moral superiority, is confronted in this letter with negative behaviour that failed to correspond to the moral standards upheld by the Confederation. A deep sense of disappointment permeates Nesládek’s letter, and he concludes by announcing his resignation from the Council of the Prague branch.

Nevertheless, the disputes Jan Nesládek writes about were not unprecedented and had accompanied the Confederation almost since its foundation. At that time, membership of the Confederation was a contentious issue, with disputes not only over who was eligible for membership but also over who was not eligible. From its inception, the Confederation presented itself as an association of morally upright individuals who, due to their anti-communist dedication and the subsequent suffering that ensued, were deemed entitled to determine the future political development of the country. The Confederation came to be understood as an internally exclusive group, reluctant to accept individuals lacking experience of imprisonment within its ranks. This attitude stemmed from the long and complex process of identity formation among political prisoners, both during their period of incarceration and in the aftermath of their release – a period marked by further stigmatization and harassment directed at the prisoners themselves and their families. Consequently, they devised numerous strategies to foster a favourable self-perception. The adoption of stereotypical and categorizing labels in prison (political and criminal prisoners, guards) facilitated this process, enabling them to ascribe positive traits to their group, adhere to a moral value system, and engage in self-improvement and education.⁸⁷ This stereotyping was accompanied by a process of polarization, which from a psychological point of view is an important form of response to threat. According to psychological research, the simplification of reality into discrete categories provides individuals with an enhanced sense of control over their environment.⁸⁸ This polarized view

⁸⁶ NA, coll. KPV, box 130, Letter from Jan Nesládek to KPV, 14. 7. 1993. Jan Nesládek (1925–1996) was arrested in 1949 and sentenced to twelve years’ imprisonment for his activities in an anti-communist group. He was released in 1957. He was one of the founders of K 231 in 1968 and was involved in the creation of the Confederation of Political Prisoners in 1989. He also assisted its members with administrative tasks related to judicial rehabilitation.

⁸⁷ PINEROVÁ, K.: *Do konce života*, pp. 299–302.

⁸⁸ WU, James Shyan-Tau – HAUERT, Christoph – KREMEN, Claire – ZHAO, Jiaying: *A Framework on Polarization, Cognitive Inflexibility, and Rigid Cognitive Specialization*.

of the world not only translated into their worldview and narrative, but also into the functioning of their organization.⁸⁹

As the Statutes were gradually clarified, it became evident who was and was not eligible for membership of the organization. This led to heated debates in several phases, centring on whether any members were affiliated with the Communist Party or had collaborated with the State Security. This struggle for a “morally pure and unencumbered” organization became a recurrent source of conflict. The inability of the disputing parties to reach a compromise was partly attributable to their long-standing polarization, as highly polarized individuals tend to exhibit cognitive rigidity. This is characterized by an incapacity to adjust or modify one’s cognitive processes, thereby hindering the ability to adapt to novel information or environmental changes. In summary, highly polarized individuals often adhere tenaciously to their existing beliefs and habits, sometimes to the extent that this proves actively detrimental to their well-being.⁹⁰ Conflicts emerged both at the management level and within the various branches.

In light of the pervasive fear of a resurgence of communism in society, and the frequent emergence of warnings concerning “communist cliques” emanating from various places, it is not surprising that even among the political prisoners there were fears of “traitors” or, as they were called in prison, “snitches” (*bonzáci*). However, prior to the escalation of tensions surrounding the “purity” of the organization, the Confederation was embroiled in an entirely different matter. A significant turning point occurred with the publication of a controversial “revelation” in October 1990. The essay, entitled *Analýza událostí 17. listopadu 1989* [An Analysis of the Events of 17 November 1989], was authored by Miroslav Dolejší, a member of the Confederation and a political prisoner in the 1950s and the 1970s.⁹¹ The central theme of the essay was that the Velvet Revolution of 1989 was a pre-planned operation orchestrated by foreign secret services and designed to ensure a seamless transfer of power from the communist elites to a new ruling class. The essay asserted that the superficial changes observed were, in fact, a façade, and that the underlying structure and dynamics of society remained largely unchanged. The essay also contained anti-Semitic themes insofar as it suggested

In: *Frontiers in Psychology*, No. 13 (2022), Article No. 776891, pp. 1–7. [Accessed 2025-12-04.] Available online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.776891/full>.

⁸⁹ DAVID, Roman: *Communists and Their Victims: The Quest for Justice in the Czech Republic*. Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press 2018, p. 105.

⁹⁰ WU, J. S. – HAUERT, Ch. – KREMEN, C. – ZHAO, J.: A Framework on Polarization, Cognitive Inflexibility, and Rigid Cognitive Specialization, p. 3.

⁹¹ See footnote no. 50.

that international Jewish elites or clandestine networks were responsible for the events in question. Moreover, it conveyed stereotypes about Jewish power through rhetoric implying Jewish control of the media, finance, and politics.⁹² The views under discussion were presented by the author prior to publication at the “August and the Communist Party” rally held on 21 August 1990 for the anniversary of the invasion of the Warsaw Pact troops. The text was originally intended for the September meeting of Confederation members.⁹³

The Central Committee of the Confederation initially agreed with the opening sections of the text; however, the radical and anti-Semitic tenor of the essay ultimately resulted in the rejection of the *Analýza*.⁹⁴ Dolejší defended himself by claiming that he had originally written the *Analýza* for the needs of the Confederation and had obtained the materials for it as a member of the Citizens' Commissions (*občanská komise*) operating in the Federal Ministry of the Interior in the spring of 1990, whose aim was to verify the reliability and integrity of individual members of the security forces.⁹⁵ However, Dolejší soon faced mounting criticism within the Confederation and was advised to limit his public activities.⁹⁶ Subsequently, suspicions emerged that he had been a collaborator of the State Security, which provided the grounds for his expulsion from the organization. On 8 July 1991, a Conciliation Commission (*smírčí komise*) of the Confederation was convened not only with Miroslav Dolejší but also with František Michálek, a member of the Federal Assembly, whom the Investigation Commission of this same body had found to be a collaborator of the State Security.⁹⁷ Because Michálek failed to appear at the Conciliation Commission meeting, he was expelled from the Confederation. Dolejší attempted to defend himself before the Conciliation Commission by claiming that he had signed the collaboration agree-

⁹² See SUK, J.: Politické hry s „nedokončenou revolucí“, p. 302; TOMEK, Prokop: Tragický případ Miroslava Dolejšího a Eugena Vrby. In: *Soudobé dějiny*, Vol. 16, No. 2-3 (2009), pp. 419-435.

⁹³ SUK, J.: Politické hry s „nedokončenou revolucí“, p. 302.

⁹⁴ TOMÁŠ, Josef - VOŘÍŠEK, Jaroslav: Původní rozhovor s M. Dolejším pro TP. In: *Týdeník Politika: Soukromý list pro politiku a ekonomiku*, Vol. 1, No. 28 (8-14 August 1991), pp. 2-4; NA, coll. KPV, box 136, Jan Nešládek: Kam míří klín, November 1990.

⁹⁵ TOMEK, P.: Tragický případ Miroslava Dolejšího a Eugena Vrby, p. 427.

⁹⁶ TOMÁŠ, J. - VOŘÍŠEK, J.: Původní rozhovor s M. Dolejším pro TP.

⁹⁷ The Federal Assembly Investigation Commission for Clarification of the Events of 17 November 1989 (*Vyšetřovací komise Federálního shromáždění pro objasnění událostí 17. listopadu 1989*) was established by the Federal Assembly on 20 September 1990. Its primary task was to clarify the events surrounding 17 November, including the underlying causes, the consequences, and the identification of responsibility for the violence directed at the demonstrators. The final report of the commission, dated 28 January 1992, focused exclusively on the events of 17 November 1989.

ment in order to warn his friends. However, the Conciliation Commission did not accept this as a valid defence and proposed his expulsion.⁹⁸ Dolejší ended his membership on 8 October 1991 by his own decision.⁹⁹ Czech historian Prokop Tomek researched Dolejší's alleged collaboration with the State Security and discovered that, although Dolejší had signed an agreement with the stated aim of protecting his colleagues, his name did not appear in any of the available State Security records.¹⁰⁰

The polarized worldview of the former political prisoners, which tended to evaluate actions in isolation and without broader context, led to proposals for the expulsion of not only Dolejší but also other members. We have no precise data on how many people were expelled from the Confederation; however, one hundred members of the Prague branch were allegedly expelled in this manner.¹⁰¹ The fact that Dolejší had long been in conflict with the chairman Pernický and Struska, and that his activities and writings did not reflect well on the organization, played an important role in the conflict surrounding this case.¹⁰²

In 1991, the Confederation was rocked by a scandal involving allegations that State Security agents were present in the leadership of the Confederation. On 12 March 1991, it was decided that the entire Enlarged Committee would be lustrated.¹⁰³ However, aware that they would not receive a positive lustration certificate, the members of the committee were in no hurry to undergo the procedure. The whole affair eventually led to the convening of an extraordinary meeting on 21 September, at which a completely new committee (the Council) was elected, excluding the accused members.¹⁰⁴

⁹⁸ NA, coll. KPV, box 1, Minutes of the extended committee meeting of the Confederation, 10. 7. 1991.

⁹⁹ *Ibidem*, Minutes of the KPVČ Council meeting, 15. 4. 1992; TOMÁŠ, J. – VOŘÍŠEK, J.: Původní rozhovor s M. Dolejším pro TP.

¹⁰⁰ TOMEK, P.: Tragický případ Miroslava Dolejšího a Eugena Vrby, p. 427.

¹⁰¹ NA, coll. KPV, box 129, Otevřený dopis ÚV KPV – smírčí komise [Open letter to the Central Committee of the Confederation of Political Prisoners – Conciliation Commission], 1. 11. 1994.

¹⁰² TOMÁŠ, J. – VOŘÍŠEK, J.: Původní rozhovor s M. Dolejším pro TP.

¹⁰³ NA, coll. KPV, box 1, Minutes from the extended committee meeting of the Confederation of Political Prisoners, 12. 3. 1991.

¹⁰⁴ Stanislav Drobny was elected chairman, Miloš Adámek, Zdeněk Uchytíl, Jitka Kvochová were elected vice-chairpersons. Political Commission: Bohuslav Hubálek; Defence and Security Commission: Karel Bajer; Documentation Commission: Radek Žák; Social and Health Commission: Naděžda Kavalírová; Agricultural Commission: Jan Broj; Organizational and Coordination Commission: Stanislav Cába; Economic Commission: Jaroslav Sedláček; Legal Commission: Jan Pospíšil; Without function: Richard Doležal, Ladislav Vyskočil; Revision Commission: Alois Novotný, Václav Findejs, Jiří Procházka, Naděžda Buriánková;

Another series of conflicts followed the publication of the so-called Cibulka lists (*Cibulkovy seznamy*), which appeared shortly before the June 1992 Czechoslovak parliamentary elections. Petr Cibulka, an anti-communist radical, dissident and political prisoner from the period of normalization, published thousands of names of real or alleged collaborators of the State Security in the magazine *Ty rudá krávo / Necenzurované noviny* [You Red Cow / Uncensored Newspaper] without any further explanation. These lists caused an uproar among political prisoners.¹⁰⁵ One of the main leaders who vigorously advocated for the purge of the Confederation was Stanislav Stránský,¹⁰⁶ the chairman of the largest branch in Prague. However, the conflict between Stanislav Stránský and the Confederation leadership had erupted long before the appearance of the Cibulka lists.

This very complicated and long-standing dispute between Stránský and the leadership of the Confederation has two distinct dimensions. The first concerns a conflict between two chairmen – the chairman of the Confederation and the chairman of the largest branch – regarding powers and their alleged overstepping. Stanislav Drobný pointed out that only the Chairperson, or a spokesperson appointed by him or her, was entitled to speak for the Confederation as a whole, whereas Stránský repeatedly exceeded this authority. As a result of these discussions, the Statutes were amended to more precisely define the function of the branches. Stránský interpreted this as an attempt to silence him and to forbid public speaking.¹⁰⁷ These disputes, which were never adequately resolved, soon escalated into additional conflicts.

This dispute also had a significant moral dimension, concerning the struggle for the “purification” of the organization and the removal of all persons

Court of Honour: Ladislav Lidák, Ivo Fiedler, Radoslav Krček, Antonín Misík. (*Ibidem*, box 6, Předsednictvo Rady KPVČ [Presidium of the KPVČ Council], 1991.)

¹⁰⁵ SUK, J.: Anatomy of the End of Charter 77, p. 684.

¹⁰⁶ Stanislav Stránský (1922–2012) was a political prisoner who was arrested in 1950 and sentenced to fourteen years in labour camps at the uranium mines in the Jáchymov region. He was released in 1960. After November 1989, he became actively involved in the renewal of civic life and emerged as an important representative of the Confederation of Political Prisoners, where he headed the largest Prague branch until 1994. After a series of long-standing conflicts with the Confederation’s leadership, he founded a new organization in 1994, the Association of Former Political Prisoners in the Czech Republic (*Sdružení bývalých politických vězňů České republiky*, SBPV-ČR), of which he was chairman until his death.

¹⁰⁷ NA, coll. KPV, box 131, Čestný soud na návrh předsedy JUDR. St[anislava] Drobného z KPVČ proti předsedovi Pražské pobočky KPVČ Stanislavu Stránskému [Court of Honour on the Motion of JUDR. Stanislav Drobný, Chairman of the KPVČ against Stanislav Stránský, chairman of the Prague Branch of the KPVČ], 9. 12. 1992; *ibidem*, Letter from Stanislav Drobný to Stanislav Stránský, 18. 9. 1992; *ibidem*, Odvolání na zápis rady [Appeal against the Wording of the Minutes of the Council Meeting], 24. 11. 1992.

associated with the Communist Party. In this, Stránský was not at odds with the majority of the Confederation's members. Collaboration with the hated Communist Party and the even more hated State Security was regarded as one of the unforgivable acts that threatened prisoners behind bars and endangered their lives after release. In this regard, political prisoners were united in their opinion, and the enforcement of these exclusive clauses in the Statute met with no resistance. However, Stránský's radical anti-communist stance, coupled with his unyielding temperament, led him into numerous confrontations with others. He accused the first chairman, Rudolf Pernický, of collaborating with the Communist Party. The basis for this accusation was purportedly Pernický's involvement in the Rehabilitation Committee of the Union of Anti-Fascist Fighters (*Svaz protifašistických bojovníků*, SPB) in 1969. Following the end of the Second World War, the SPB became a unifying body representing individuals who had fought against fascism and Nazism, political prisoners and those imprisoned in Nazi concentration and extermination camps. During the Prague Spring, the SPB played a pivotal role in the establishment of the Rehabilitation Act and subsequently established a network of rehabilitation counselling centres and commissions to advise those seeking rehabilitation.¹⁰⁸ Pernický participated in the activities of one of these counselling centres. Consequently, the accusation of Pernický's collaboration with communists was not well founded. This dispute eventually led to a civil lawsuit, which Stránský ultimately lost.

As late as 1991, Stránský accused the Confederation leadership of having among its founding members and committee members individuals who had cooperated with the State Security.¹⁰⁹ Subsequent evidence, as documented in official records, confirmed the veracity of Stránský's assertions in this regard.¹¹⁰ Conversely, after

¹⁰⁸ PINEROVÁ, Klára: Nedokončená spravedlnost: Role Svazu protifašistických bojovníků v rehabilitačním procesu (1968–1970). In: *Soudobé dějiny / Czech Journal of Contemporary History*, Vol. 31, No. 1 (2024), pp. 63–88.

¹⁰⁹ NA, coll. KPV, box 131, Letter from Stanislav Drobný to the Council of the Local Branch of the KPV, 16. 6. 1993.

¹¹⁰ Among the founding members, according to the name registers of the Security Services Archive (*Jmenné evidence Archivu bezpečnostních složek*, ABS) in Prague, the following persons were identified as collaborators: Hilda Hojerová-Čiháková (Matylda Hojerová, born 9. 12. 1909, reg. no. 2688, file opened on 17 May 1956, code name: Hilda, category: not specified, file closed on 17 January 1958, arch. no. 42915); František Melichar (born 7. 10. 1920, file opened on 28 June 1979, reg. no. 18086, code name Michal, category A (Agent), arch. no. 806185); Čeněk Sovák (born 18. 1. 1923, file opened on 29 August 1978, reg. no. 15750, code name: Conductor, Category A (Agent), file destroyed on 4 December 1989); Jitka Pufflerová-Rybáková (Jitka Rybáková, born 3. 1. 1930, file opened on 1 September 1954, reg. no. 3736, code name: Rosana, category: not specified, arch. no. 34750). For Melichar's cooperation in prison, see the edited interview with him in: MELICHAROVÁ, Jana: *Vězeňská zařízení Vojna a Bytíz*

the re-election of the Confederation Council in September 1991, no suspicions remained concerning any member of the Council. The Confederation leadership itself subsequently called for lustration. Individuals whose names appeared on the Cibulka lists were required to submit a clean lustration certificate.¹¹¹ Some of those accused responded to this demand with a letter to Stanislav Drobný, in which they demanded an end to the “smear campaign”.¹¹²

The conflict between the Confederation leadership, represented by Drobný and Stránský, escalated in 1992 and 1993, affecting other individuals, including the editors of the magazine *Věrní zůstali*. This periodical was published by the Prague branch, and it featured several articles that were disparaging towards the leadership of the Confederation.¹¹³ Consequently, Ladislav Jirásek, a member of the editorial board, was required to defend these articles before the Court of Honour (*čestný soud*).¹¹⁴ The Confederation split into two factions: one group supported Stránský – primarily individuals from the Prague branch – while the other sided with Drobný and expressed their support in written correspondence.¹¹⁵

Stanislav Stránský’s uncompromising approach did not pay off, and the Prague branch itself eventually turned against him, accusing him of failing to convene members’ meetings, failing to communicate, and neglecting to submit reports

na Příbramsku v pamětech politických vězňů: Životní příběhy. Masters dissertation. Praha, Pedagogická fakulta Univerzity Karlovy 2004. For additional names, see BARTOŠ, Adam B.: Konfederaci politických vězňů spoluzakládala StB, bývalý šéf má po letech důkaz [online]. [Accessed 2025-11-28.] Available at: https://www.idnes.cz/zpravy/domaci/konfederaci-politicky-ch-veznu-spoluzakladala-stb-byvaly-sef-ma-po-letech-dukaz.A080326_120746_domaci_adb.

¹¹¹ NA, coll. KPV, box 131, Minutes of the KPVČ Council meeting, 17. 6. 1992. In June 1992, 42 of 57 members of the KPVČ Council turned in clean lustration certificates.

¹¹² *Ibidem*, box 130, Letter to Stanislav Drobný, 10. 3. 1992. This letter was signed by: Hilda Hojerová-Čiháková, Jitka Pufflerová, Roman Sakmar, Vladimír Struska, Milan Eichler, Radek Žák, František Zahrádka, Josef Slanina, Jiří Krbec, Rudolf Pernický, (?) Brož, and two more unidentified signatures.

¹¹³ *Ibidem*, box 129, Letter from Stanislav Drobný and Miroslav Kostelka to the branches of the KPV, 14. 7. 1993.

¹¹⁴ *Ibidem*, box 130, Letter from L. Jirásek, L. Pánek, V. Šišková, A. Kroužek, M. Hašek [probably addressed to all members of the KPV], undated, probably 1993; *ibidem*, Návrh na svolání Čestného soudu podle stanov KPVČ [Proposal to Convene the Court of Honour in Accordance with the KPVČ Statutes], 1. 9. 1993; *ibidem*, Stanovisko Čestného soudu při KPV [Opinion of the Court of Honour at the KPV], 6. 10. 1993; *ibidem*, Letter from Ladislav Jirásek [probably addressed to all members of the KPV], 17. 5. 1993.

¹¹⁵ *Ibidem*, box 131, Prohlášení zástupců moravských poboček KPVČ [Statement by Representatives of the Moravian Branches of KPVČ], 29. 4. 1993; *ibidem*, Letter from Stanislav Stránský [probably addressed to all members of the KPV], probably 1993.

on the branch's financial management.¹¹⁶ All this led to his removal as chairman in 1994. This dispute had two further consequences. One was a lawsuit for libel brought by the Confederation, which Stránský ultimately lost.¹¹⁷ The second was the establishment of another organization, the Association of Former Political Prisoners of the Czech Republic (*Sdružení bývalých politických vězňů České republiky*, SBPV-ČR), which Stránský chaired for a long time.¹¹⁸ The animosity between these organizations persists and they have not cooperated in any way. At an early stage, it was even proposed to amend the Statutes to prohibit a political prisoner from being a member of both organizations.¹¹⁹ However, this proposal did not succeed.

The years 1992–1994 were a turbulent period during which disputes arose not only within the leadership but also in the branches. These disputes had a significant impact on the organization, leading to a marked weakening of its structures. In 1994, the political prisoner Zdeněk Otruba wrote: “The helplessness of the KPV leadership, the inability to assert itself politically, the internal quarrels, the mutual accusations within and the wholesale anti-communism outside – all these can only be symptoms of the deep, inevitable disintegration of the political prisoners’ movement. With the gradual loss of moral credibility in the eyes of the nation, political prisoners are becoming a somewhat comical coterie of quarrelsome old men to whom others listen with half an ear and thinly disguised impatience. This is a situation that the nation does not deserve.”¹²⁰ It was only in the second half of the 1990s that these disputes began to de-escalate. Although these disputes led to further organizational closure and increased internal polarization, the Confederation still provided its members with the opportunity to meet and maintain an environment of sharing and mutual understanding.

¹¹⁶ *Ibidem*, box 130, Stanovisko nové pobočky KPV Praha 150 k současné situaci ve společenství bývalých politických vězňů III. odboje v Praze [Statement by the New Branch of KPV Prague 150 on the Current Situation in the Community of Former Political Prisoners of the Third Resistance in Prague], 12. 4. 1994.

¹¹⁷ *Ibidem*, box 131, Rozsudek [Judgment] 8C 96/96, 16. 4. 1997; *ibidem*, žaloba na [lawsuit against] Stanislava Stránského, 26. 9. 1995.

¹¹⁸ *Ibidem*, box 129, Vinohradské setkání [Vinohrady meeting], undated.

¹¹⁹ *Ibidem*, box 128, Návrh Stanov KPV ČR od Dušana Chvala, Pobočka KPV ČR č. 15 [Draft Statutes of the KPV ČR by Dušan Chval, Branch of the KPV ČR No. 15], June 1995.

¹²⁰ Quoted in: HALLA, J.: *Organizace bývalých politických vězňů* [online], pp. 97–98.

Conclusion

In the early years following the collapse of the dictatorship of the Communist Party, the Confederation of Political Prisoners established itself as a prominent organization that sought not only the rehabilitation and compensation of its members, but also broader social and political transformation. The Confederation endeavoured to preserve the memory of communist repression and to promote consistent decommunization, including the condemnation and punishment of the crimes of communism. While the Confederation achieved notable success in implementing legislation to support former political prisoners and in exposing the transgressions of communist regimes, its evolution has been characterized by internal discord, ideological strife, and a gradual erosion of unity.

From its inception, the Confederation faced the question of its major goals. In its early stages, it adopted objectives analogous to those of its antecedent K 231. Primarily, the aims of Confederation included the swift rehabilitation and compensation of victims of communist repression, along with the provision of benefits to its constituents, such as discounted holiday vouchers, affordable telephone tariffs, and complimentary transportation, emulating the provisions extended to the members of the First and Second Resistance. These demands were rapidly supplemented in the early months of the Velvet Revolution by calls for recognition of their historical role in the fall of communism, i.e. acknowledgement of the anti-communist (Third) Resistance. In contrast to the period of the Prague Spring, this emerged as a wholly novel demand, arising from the prevailing political environment and the long-term evolution of their identity as political prisoners and adversaries of communism. They did not regard themselves as mere victims. This created a tension between their self-constructed identity and the image accepted by the public. This discord led to a deepening of existing misunderstandings and to profound disillusionment among the political prisoners, who perceived that society did not adequately recognize their anti-communist activities.¹²¹

The Confederation's approach to the political developments in Czechoslovakia (and later in the Czech Republic) proved to be a pivotal moment in determining its subsequent trajectory. Within the organization, there were discussions about the possibility of greater involvement in the political process as a political party. Ultimately, the prevailing sentiment favoured maintaining the Confederation as an autonomous entity, envisaged as a moral compass for political subjects and an overseer of their activities. Despite endeavours to exert influence over the political landscape, the Confederation's representatives found themselves disillusioned by the perceived lack of consideration for their viewpoint. In response,

¹²¹ MAYER, F.: *Češi a jejich komunismus*, pp. 181–187.

during the second parliamentary elections (June 1992), a strategic shift in tactics emerged, as the organization sought to adopt a more proactive stance by offering its support to political entities and individuals aligned with its positions on decommunization and the acknowledgement of anti-communist resistance. This included the participation of certain members as candidates for various political groups. However, their success rate was minimal.

Following the Velvet Revolution, a variety of new issues emerged in the Czechoslovak public sphere. Discussions among political representatives and in public often displayed a marked degree of radicalism, stemming from the prolonged suppression of dissenting views during the communist rule. At the time of their arrest, political prisoners formed a heterogeneous group united primarily by their shared experience of imprisonment. While they were initially united by their collective enthusiasm for the fall of the communist dictatorship in 1989, tensions soon began to emerge, leading to numerous conflicts. A significant factor in these internal disputes was the question of membership. Gradually, a polarizing “us versus them” approach took hold, rooted in the prison environment where it had functioned as a survival strategy and shaped by the belief that the communist dictatorship was absolute evil. The Confederation thus began to profile itself as a “morally pure” organization, leaving no place for anyone connected with the former regime in any way. These disputes led to deep divisions within the association and sharp personal conflicts, ultimately resulting in the formation of a rival organization: the Association of Former Political Prisoners of the Czech Republic.

The early 1990s represented completely new and unexplored territory for political prisoners and their newly formed organization. It offered them the opportunity to promote their interests at a societal level and share their experiences of persecution with a wider audience, after decades of forced silence. Although it might seem that the Confederation was unsuccessful in its efforts, the reality is more nuanced. This study has focused in particular on their perceived influence on policy development. While the Confederation’s members did not succeed in placing their own representatives in parliament, they achieved notable successes in the legislative sphere, as well as in shaping public narratives and collective memory. In the long term, the Confederation became a key player in transitional justice and in the broader process of defining and legitimizing the new values of post-1989 developments. The organization promoted an anti-communist framework as one of the central values of the democratic order after the fall of communism, using narratives of suffering and resistance as essential tools of moral and political authority.

Although this narrative failed to gain traction through direct participation in parliamentary politics, the Confederation employed other strategies that proved effective in the long term. It gradually aligned itself with conservative political

parties, especially the Civic Democratic Party and the Christian and Democratic Union – Czechoslovak People’s Party, which adopted part of its agenda and incorporated anti-communism into their political identity. This process became particularly evident after 2000, in conjunction with the evolution of memory politics, and continues to some extent today. At the same time, the Confederation promoted its narrative through activities that could be perceived as apolitical, such as commemorative events to remember victims of the communist dictatorship. However, due to their nature and the participation of political representatives, these events inevitably acquired a significant political dimension. Since 1990, the Confederation has organized regular and irregular commemorative events. One of the most significant is the annual “Jáchymov Hell” (*Jáchymovské peklo*) meeting, held at sites of former labour camps near uranium mines in north-western Bohemia. Prisoners there were exposed to extremely harsh working conditions and dangerous levels of radioactivity; today, these camps are widely regarded as symbols of communist repression. Another notable event is the annual “Prisoners’ Pilgrimage” (*Muklovská pout’*) at Svatý Hostýn, an important Marian place of pilgrimage in the Western Carpathians, where a memorial to the victims of communism was unveiled in 1994 in the presence of KPV representatives and political figures. Important meetings are also held in the Ďáblice and Motol cemeteries in Prague, where executed or deceased political prisoners are buried. These events were regularly attended by MPs, government officials, and regional authorities. The speeches given at these events often emphasized the importance of recognizing anti-communist resistance and warned against the threat of a return to communist ideology. Thus, the Confederation established itself as a “guardian of memory”, keeping the legacy of the victims of communism alive in the public sphere.

Ultimately, the Confederation’s long-term pressure on political representatives through the media and public appearances proved effective. In 2011, after several previous unsuccessful attempts, the anti-communist resistance was finally recognized by law. However, efforts to recognize former political prisoners as fighters against communism were not confined to the legislative sphere. Since the turn of the millennium, there has been an increasing level of professional and public reflection on their legacy. This is due to younger generations of historians publishing works on the anti-communist resistance of the 1950s, non-profit organizations undertaking projects on this topic, and former political prisoners being invited to school discussions and party events. Media productions in the form of documentaries and TV series have also offered a favourable assessment of their activities. Nevertheless, this significant success was overshadowed by challenges arising from ongoing internal disagreements between the then chairwoman, Naděžda Kavalírová, and another group of former political prisoners who questioned her 2015 election. This protracted dispute over

the Confederation's leadership was not resolved until 2024. In the meantime, the Confederation's influence diminished due to the advancing age of its members.

The Confederation's example suggests that even an organization presenting itself as apolitical could play a significant role in post-1989 developments, not only in transitional justice, but also in politics and in defining new democratic values. It also shows how collective memory can become a source of political identity and legitimacy: the Confederation's activities helped establish anti-communism in the Czech environment as not only a political stance, but also a language of identity and moral authority in the public sphere – even after the Confederation was no longer an active player.

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Abstract

In the early days of the Velvet Revolution in the autumn of 1989, former political prisoners revived the idea of creating a new organization to defend their interests, demand rehabilitation and compensation, and investigate and document the crimes of the communist dictatorship. In the weeks that followed, they decided to establish a new organization called the Confederation of Political Prisoners of Czechoslovakia (Konfederace politických vězňů Československa, KPV), which rapidly expanded its membership and within a few months had more than 16,000 members and more than eighty regional branches. This membership base was interested not only in advocating for improved conditions for former political prisoners and their rehabilitation, but also in positioning itself as an important partner in ongoing political development. The Confederation's moral capital, publicly promoted in various statements and memoranda from the earliest days of the Velvet Revolution, served as an important driving force in the post-revolutionary process. It played a key role in promoting legislative measures to compensate the victims of the communist dictatorship and actively participated in the process of exposing the crimes of communism. The Confederation's activities since its establishment have been extensive, and the present article focuses primarily on its early years, during which time the Confederation confronted both internal and external challenges, ranging

from organizational growth and identity formation to the extent of its involvement in political life. The author examines how these different political, social, and economic conditions influenced the demands of the Confederation and the development of its strategies. While the article's primary focus is on the political ambitions of the Confederation – examining its role in the political struggle, as well as its ability to influence the political agenda – the author also addresses the internal dynamics of the organization, its efforts to purge members who had collaborated with the communist dictatorship and the resulting conflicts among its members.

Keywords:

Czechoslovakia; communism; anti-communism; political prisoners; post-communist transformation; Confederation of Political Prisoners (*Konfederace politických vězňů*, KPV); Third (anti-communist) Resistance; transitional justice; collective memory; civil society

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